

Infrastructuring social labs: Establishing a sustainable research, development, and innovation platform driven by citizen collaboration

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Abstract

In this study, we propose the concept of ‘social lab’ as a sustainable research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) platform. A social lab is a derivative of Living Labs (LLs) that emphasises R&D&I in collaboration with citizens. This paper especially describes our case study aims at ‘infrastructuring’ (i.e., establishing and sustaining) a social lab in an actual city setting. By analysing the case study process and results, we identified three key implications for effectively infrastructuring social labs: supporting the process of core member formation, leveraging existing urban resources, and establishing a coevolutionary loop between infrastructural resource development and R&D&I practices. We also revealed the challenges in infrastructuring social labs, such as human resource issues, low visibility of outcomes, and a lack of service design methods and tools.

Key words

social lab; infrastructuring; R&D&I; citizen involvement; case study

Introduction

Digital technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and big data processing have become essential components of our lives, and the digitisation of society is rapidly progressing. Additionally, ‘smart city’ initiatives that use and integrate various digital (smart) technologies in city settings are being actively promoted. While digital technologies have a strong potential to create a better future society, there is growing concern about their negative impacts on society, such as the loss of human autonomy and breaches of privacy [1]. In addition, some researchers and journalists have strongly criticised technology-driven approaches to smart city initiatives and argued for the importance of human-centric smart cities [2]. Against this backdrop, emphasis has recently been placed on the inclusion of social and ethical considerations in technical research and development (R&D) process [3].

To use digital technologies to positively affect society and realise human-centric innovation, we should focus not only on developing the technology itself but also on designing a ‘service system [4]’ that includes technologies as its components to create social value [5]. In other words, we should go beyond R&D for core technology development; rather, we should focus on the integration of R&D and subsequent Innovation processes (hereafter, R&D&I), where innovation activities can be regarded as a process of designing service systems [6]. Considering the potential negative impacts of digital technologies, the involvement of ‘citizens’ directly affected by technologies in the R&D&I process is important. Furthermore, to generate continuous and varied innovations, we should establish a sustainable platform for co-creation that supports various R&D&I projects.

Living Lab (LL), an innovation approach driven by co-creation with citizens and other stakeholders (e.g. [7]), is expected to be an effective means of realising the R&D&I platform [6]. Recently, many LL projects have focused on innovation based on co-creation with users (citizens), and often include research and innovation processes [8]. However, few studies have discussed how to establish an LL from a viewpoint of an R&D&I platform for human-centric innovation.

In this study, we first propose the concept of ‘social lab’ as a sustainable R&D&I platform in a city. We then describe our case study, which was promoted for several years, to investigate the establishment of a social lab in an actual city setting. Finally, through an in-depth analysis of the case, we discuss our findings on the key activities and challenges for

effectively establishing and sustaining social labs.

Background

Designing service systems in R&D&I context

In the context of human-centric innovation, the focus should be on ‘services’ that include technology as its component, rather than on technology itself. In service research, the concept of a service system is defined as ‘a configuration of people, technology, and other resources that interact via value propositions to create mutual value [4].’ As this definition indicates, technology should be developed and integrated to enhance value creation in service systems. Designing service systems is therefore a particularly important approach for R&D&I, especially for the ‘I (innovation)’ context.

In academia, the approach to designing service systems has been discussed in the field of service design (SD) studies (e.g. [9]). In SD, various methods and tools have been developed to support the service system design, including user behaviour analysis, value analysis, business model design, and service process design.

LLs for human-centric innovation

According to ENoLL (European Networks of Living Labs), the world’s largest community on LLs, LLs are defined as ‘user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings [10].’ LL aims for human-centric innovation and often involves research activities. Furthermore, LL is positioned as an open innovation approach based on the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM), in which four types of stakeholders—citizens, industries, government, and academia—collaboratively work for social innovation [11]. These stakeholders in QHM play important roles in R&D&I; academia conducts R&D activities, industry and government act for innovation, and the citizen community strongly infuses a human-centric perspective into all the contexts of R, D, and I. This indicates that LL is an effective approach for R&D&I.

Issues on project-based nature of LLs

Continuity is one of the challenges faced by LLs when viewed as R&D&I platforms. As Hossain [8] pointed out, many LLs are promoted as project-based activities, which means

that the end of project funding is the end of LL activities. Also, in the HCI (Human-Computer Interaction) field, scholars have denoted considering ‘after-the project’ is essential in field-based research aiming to social use of technologies [12]. To extend the LL concept as an R&D&I platform, where various R&D&I projects are actively implemented, the co-creation scheme should be sustainable (i.e. not limited to the project duration) and embedded as an urban resource in a city.

Furthermore, the continuity issue is also inherent in citizen participation. Previous studies have pointed out the issue of the heavy burden on citizens in the LL process [13]. Scholars have also illustrated the difficulties in preventing users from dropping out of LL projects and explored ways to maintain their motivation in the long-term participation process. These issues essentially stem from the researcher-citizen relationship. A collaboration scheme based on an asymmetrical beneficial relationship in which researchers ‘use’ citizens for their projects, has limitations in its sustainability as an innovation ecosystem.

Social Lab as a sustainable R&D&I platform

Concept of social lab

In this study, we propose the concept of the ‘social lab’ as a sustainable R&D&I platform in a city. Hassan [14] first used the term social lab as a platform aimed at tackling complex social problems with multiple actors. The authors also define the social lab from the R&D&I context as ‘an R&D&I scheme to foster a socially acceptable implementation of digital technologies in the service form through cooperation with citizens [6].’ This social lab concept can be regarded as a derivative of LLs, which emphasise the context of R&D&I in collaboration with citizens.

This study extends the existing concept of social labs by highlighting the perspective of sustainable R&D&I platform. Figure 1 presents a conceptual sketch of the social lab proposed in this study. This concept has four key facets: the first three are based on our previous social lab concept [6] and the fourth is newly added in this study.

(1) Integration of SD and R&D

As discussed, the integration of SD and R&D is essential for developing digital technologies that create value for stakeholders and society. The insights obtained from the SD activities will support to clarify the direction of R&D. Integrating appropriate digital technologies into a service system will contribute to higher value creation and differentiation from

Figure 1. Social lab as sustainable R&D&I platform (illustrated based on [6])

competitors.

(2) Design researchers as key mediator

In this model, an R&D organisation (e.g. a university or research institute) includes two types of researchers: technology and design researchers. The design researcher acts as a mediator between the city (i.e. local organisation and community) and the R&D. They mainly promote SD activities to explore the values to be provided and design service systems with citizens and other stakeholders (e.g. companies and municipalities). Simultaneously, design researchers communicate with technology researchers to share their findings or ideas about the service systems to be realised. This mediation by design researchers will allow for successful harmonisation of technologies and service systems.

(3) Mutual learning between citizens and researchers

Citizen involvement in technology and service development is important for human-centric innovation [15]. Scholars argue that mutual learning between citizens and researchers is the core of effective co-creation [16]. Researchers, including both design and technology researchers, should learn about the context, values, and issues of local communities. Citizens must also understand digital technologies and their positive and negative impacts. The mutual learning process contributes to creating a flat and close citizen-researcher relationship and empowering the citizens.

(4) Infrastructure to support practices in R&D&I projects

This study aims to establish a social lab as a sustainable R&D&I platform. A sustainable platform indicates a long-lasting scaffolding ‘infrastructure’ to support various R&D&I projects in a city. Therefore, we conceptualise a social lab as an urban infrastructure for supporting R&D&I activities rather than as a scheme for one-time R&D&I projects with a limited duration. This is challenging in LL studies because many LL projects are project-based and discontinuous in the long term [8].

The term ‘infrastructure’ in this study is based on the concept proposed by Star and Ruhdler [17]. Infrastructure is a bundle of tangible (e.g. physical products, buildings, tools) and intangible resources (e.g. rules, knowledge, know-how, customs) that supports people’s practices [18]. Thus, establishing a social lab as an R&D&I platform requires the development of tangible and intangible infrastructural resources that effectively support various R&D&I practices. Based on Karasti’s work [19], we use the term ‘infrastructuring’ to refer to the activities of developing and embedding infrastructural resources in a city.

Infrastructural resources

Next, we discuss the infrastructural resources that should be developed in infrastructuring social labs. Previous studies reported resources that had fostered or foregrounded through infrastructuring work, such as actor network and trust [20, 21], knowledge and skills [22], and common spaces for collaboration [23]. Interpreting these resources in the context of the social lab concept proposed in this study, we identify key resources to be focused on.

Actor network and trust

A social lab as an R&D&I platform requires a continuous citizen-researcher relationship rather than short-term collaboration for a limited time. Therefore, in terms of actor network and trust, more emphasis should be placed on the ‘*solid and long-term partnerships with citizens*’ for sustaining a social lab. Such close partnerships are also practically helpful in recruiting appropriate participants and ensuring their continuous and proactive participation in R&D&I projects.

Besides citizens, as argued in previous studies, R&D&I projects in a social lab must also collaborate with practitioners and experts who are active in a city on the social issue or industry focused on the project. For example, a project related to the healthcare of the elderly should involve collaboration with local daycare centres and hospitals. To

collaborate with the appropriate actors in each R&D&I project, a ‘local actor network’ is essential as a resource for supporting a social lab.

Knowledge and skills

To achieve active and long-term citizen participation in R&D&I projects, we should focus on the development of appropriate attitudes (or mindset) in addition to knowledge and skills, as Kirkpatrick’s KSAs (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes) model [24] argued.

Namely, the actors involved in the social lab (citizens, industry, government, and researchers) preferably have KSAs that positively affect R&D&I projects (hereafter, ‘KSAs for R&D&I’). For example, in terms of knowledge, it is important for citizens to have the right knowledge (i.e. literacy) of digital technologies; for researchers, knowing about the local community is important. In terms of skills, creative thinking skills are required to tackle complex social issues and collaboration with others are required [25]. Attitudes include, for example, an interest in local issues and the design attitude [26] for actively exploring solutions to local issues. These KSAs are intangible resources which are difficult to measure, but are important for making collaborative R&D&I projects more effective.

Furthermore, in terms of knowledge and skills of design researchers, ‘methods and tools’ for SD in the R&D&I context are important to be developed. In the R&D&I context, design researchers should consider not only value creation for citizens and society but also technological R&D and the use of technologies. This design problem is more complex than a general SD problem, which focuses primarily on the value aspect. Therefore, methods and tools to support this complex design task should be developed and provided as infrastructural resources to enhance the KSAs for SD activities in social labs.

Common spaces for collaboration

From the viewpoint of spaces, R&D&I projects in social labs use various locations in a city. For example, in the initial phase of R&D&I, collaborative discussions on future vision and conceptual design are often held in workshop spaces. R&D&I projects also require physical locations to promote experiments on the technologies or services developed in the project. These ‘spaces for design and experiment’ should be provided to actors as highly accessible resources that can be used immediately when they want to use.

In summary, we identify five key resources to be developed in infrastructuring social lab: (1) solid and long-term partnerships with citizens, (2) local actor network, (3) KSAs for R&D&I, (4) methods and tools, and (5) spaces for design and experiments.

Infrastructuring a social lab

Case study

To deeply investigate how to establish a social lab, this study adopted the design case study approach demonstrated by Dalsgaard and Eriksson [27]. We played the roles of design practitioners and researchers. On the one hand, we actively promoted various activities to establish a social lab as a practitioner; on the other hand, we analysed our own processes as researchers to clarify the key activities and challenges for effectively infrastructuring social labs. In general, this type of single case study is effective for deeply investigating a particular topic in a unique context [28]. We therefore did not aim to present a universal conclusion that can be applied to all cases or contexts. Instead, we aim to provide findings that are practically helpful to other practitioners and researchers working in areas related to this study.

The case we focused on was the project where the authors have been working to establish a social lab since 2019. We played the role of ‘design researcher’ in Figure 1. The research institutes to which some authors belong are engaged in R&D activities on digital technologies such as robotics, motion analysis, healthcare, and sensing. We attempted to establish a social lab in a city where our research institute is located to realise the social use of such advanced technologies and subsequent human-centric innovation.

The city where the case study was conducted is Kashiwa-no-ha, a suburban area of Tokyo. It is one of the most famous smart cities in Japan, where leading universities, research institutes, and various companies are located. The area near the station is mainly populated by relatively young residents (in their 30s-40s) and their families; older residents live in residential areas a short distance from the station.

Infrastructuring activities

This section describes the details of our infrastructuring process in a social lab corresponding to the five key resources identified in Section 3.2.

The infrastructuring process described below was analysed to investigate how to effectively promote the infrastructuring work of a social lab. To this end, we used multiple data sources such as public reports, materials used in the planning phase, and field notes. The analysis results, namely our findings related to key activities and challenges in

infrastructural social labs, are described in Section 5.

(1) Solid and long-term partnership with citizens

To create a solid citizen-researcher partnership, we started a ‘citizen advisor’ program in November 2019 [6]. This program is unique as it aims to organize a more general citizen community of those interested in advanced technologies and social lab activities, rather than a group of citizen participants for a specific project. After the community started, COVID-19 spread across Japan and the world. We therefore held the regular virtual café talk meetings once or twice a month in 2020 for maintaining the relationship with citizens. This continuous communication between citizens and researchers helped to build trust and closer relationships.

(2) Local actor network

To build the local actor network necessary for the social lab, we tried to build relationships with various local actors in addition to citizens. At that time, we realised that an invisible local actor network had already been established in the city and it would be better to be incorporated as a member of the existing network than to build a new one. We thus first tried to build a relationship with an area management organisation, which is a key actor in the local actor network. The organisation has played a central role in the area management of the smart city for many years; therefore, it has a wide and strong network with various local actors. By leveraging the organisation’s existing network, we could access and communicate with a wide range of local actors (e.g. shopping centres, bus companies, and public park management organisations) in several R&D&I projects described in Section 4.3. This process was really effective to become a part of local actor network and build relationships with specific actors in the network when needed.

(3) Knowledge, skill, and attitude

To foster KSAs for R&D&I as infrastructural resources, we started to provide the ‘mini-school program’ for citizens in 2021. The mini-school programs had two categories: technology and design. Technology mini-schools (Tech-MS) aimed to provide an opportunity for citizens to learn about advanced digital technologies. We organised Tech-MS three times in 2021; in each program, researchers first demonstrated a digital technology; subsequently, citizens and researchers collaboratively discussed the potential benefits and threats of the technology. Meanwhile, the design mini-schools (Des-MS) provided a training program to teach creative mindsets and co-creation skills. The Des-MS was also provided three times in 2021. In fact, skills for creativity and collaboration cannot be fully acquired through this kind of short-term training sessions; however, they are

valuable for citizen participants as they allowed them to experience new mindsets and ways of thinking.

(4) Methods and tools

To develop an infrastructural resource for supporting SD activities in a social lab, we developed several SD methods and tools. For example, we proposed a method to support the conceptual design of service systems that can holistically consider three domains: social (e.g. strategies and citizen values), digital (e.g. digital technologies and data), and physical (e.g. physical products and urban resources) systems [29]. Other, we developed the ‘participation blueprint’ method to systematically design the long-term citizen participation process [30]. These methods were exploratory developed to overcome difficulties encountered in R&D&I activities in the social lab.

(5) Spaces for design and experiments

In terms of the physical spaces needed for the social lab, we explored the opportunity to use the existing spaces to organise design workshops and social experiments. Fortunately, because the field was a smart city, the culture and facilities encouraging new initiatives such as workshops and experiments were available. This strategy also helped to avoid the large costs to develop and set up new physical spaces.

For the design workshop, we primarily used digital spaces (i.e. web conference services) during the COVID-19 pandemic. After the pandemic began to subside, we could use physical workshop spaces owned by the area management organisation, based on the collaborative relationship constructed in advance. Regarding the space for experiments, we could conduct experiments in the real field of the city (e.g. existing facilities and public spaces) based on the collaboration with local actors. For example, in the R&D&I project related to local transportation systems, a digital signage system was experimentally installed in a large shopping centre and hotel to verify its functionality. Within the same project, automated delivery robots were also tested on public sidewalks.

Domain-specific R&D&I projects

In addition to infrastructuring activities, we promoted two R&D&I projects that dealt with specific domains. The first is an R&D&I project to develop digital technologies that support the well-being of seniors. In this project, which lasted for over four months, we visualised future visions from citizens’ viewpoints and extracted key insights into R&D&I in health and welfare technology. The second project was an R&D&I project aimed at developing

local transportation services using advanced mobility technologies. Through the collaborative and exploratory process in this project, we obtained some important insights for enhancing local transportation. Based on the insights, we developed and tested some prototypes of service systems such as a digital signage system to encourage local mobility and automated delivery robots as means of efficient goods transportation.

Findings

This section presents the findings regarding key activities and challenges for effectively infrastructuring social labs, which were identified from our case study experiences.

Key activities for infrastructuring social labs

The first key activity we found relates to the citizen-researcher relationship. In this case study, we aim to build closer relationships through mutual learning processes. As a result, some citizens became so-called ‘core members’, which refers to citizens actively participating in most events and workshops held in the social lab. These highly engaged citizen partners provided valuable opinions and comments on operating a social lab. Furthermore, some of them widely disseminated and shared their experiences in the project through personal social media accounts. These phenomena clearly indicate the importance of supporting the formation of core members to realise a sustainable social lab.

Second, we identified the importance of utilising urban resources that already exist in the city when developing infrastructural resources for social labs. In the case study, we connected our social lab activities with existing tangible and intangible resources, such as workshop spaces and actor networks. In infrastructuring studies, resources already exist in the field is referred to as ‘installed base’ [31] and using the installed base has been seen as important for penetrating our social lab activities into the city, as it meant making connections to social inertia and powers that already existed there [19]. Hence, exploring urban resources that can be leveraged to operate social labs is important in establishing social labs.

Third, we found the co-evolutionary loop between infrastructural resource development and R&D&I practices (Figure 2) contributes to building a more solid infrastructure for sustainable social labs. Prior to the case study, we assumed that infrastructural resources had a positive impact on R&D&I projects. However, through a case study, we realised the

Figure 2. Co-evolutionary loop between infrastructuring work and R&D&I projects

importance of influence in the opposite direction; the R&D&I project has also reinforced infrastructure resources. For example, some citizens who participated in a workshop held in an R&D&I project were subsequently registered as members of the citizen advisor program. This type of co-evolutionary loop between infrastructural resource development and R&D&I practices contributes to building a solid infrastructure and sustaining the social lab.

Challenges for infrastructuring social labs

First, we found the challenge relates to human resources in developing long-term relationships with citizens. In the case study, many human resources were needed to organise collaborative activities with citizens and other actors. This indicates stable human and financial support are required in social labs.

Second, infrastructure is a behind-the-scenes activity to develop resources to support future R&D&I projects, which is not easily visible. Unlike specific R&D&I projects, in which digital technologies and services are developed as an outcome, the results of infrastructuring activities tend not to be highlighted [20]. This issue should be overcome as it relates to maintaining the motivation of social lab operators.

Third, methods and tools to support SD in the social lab context have not yet been comprehensively prepared, although we have developed some original methods (see Section 4.2). Therefore, in future work, we will investigate and collect relevant existing methods and develop original methods, if required. Through such continuous SD research activities, we will develop an SD toolbox appropriate for the social lab context.

Discussion and conclusion

In this study, we proposed the concept of social lab as a sustainable R&D&I platform and described the details of our activities for infrastructuring a social lab in a city. By analysing the case study process and results, we clarified three key implications for effectively infrastructuring social labs: supporting the process of core member formation, leveraging existing urban resources (i.e. the installed bases), and establishing a coevolutionary loop between infrastructural resource development and R&D&I practices. We also revealed the challenges of infrastructuring social labs, such as human resource issues, low visibility of outcomes, and a lack of SD methods and tools.

The contributions of this study to the LL studies are summarised as follows. The first is the conceptualisation of the social lab as a sustainable R&D&I platform. The proposed social lab concept suggests a concrete relationships between four actors in LLs as QHM and indicates a new potential for expanding the LL methodology, focusing on the R&D&I perspective. Second, we present the implications for infrastructuring social labs based on our findings from a several-year case study in an actual city setting. We believe that the findings will be of practical use to future practitioners and researchers involved in social labs and projects related to this study (e.g. citizen-driven R&D&I and sustainability of LLs).

Star et al., in their research of infrastructure, emphasised the continuous process of building infrastructure; they placed more focus on the process aspect of infrastructure, namely 'how to build infrastructure' [17, 18]. This idea inspired further discussions on infrastructuring among various scholars, mainly in the field of participatory design (e.g. [19-24]). The three implications identified in this study are exactly what present concrete and practical suggestions on the process aspect of infrastructure, which focus on how to infrastructure social labs. Hence, we believe the findings of this study are not only practical but also contribute to the development of existing discussions on citizen involvement in the design of socio-technical systems.

Our in-depth analysis of the case enabled us to obtain new findings that would be difficult to identify using a more objective approach such as questionnaire-based investigations. However, the findings were derived from a single case; thus, the exhaustiveness and generality of our findings are limited. For example, Kashiwanoha Smart City, where we conducted the case study, contained urban resources for utilizing new technologies (e.g., workshop spaces and actor networks) as an installed base, whereas other cities may have few such resources. In future work, we will conduct further activities on infrastructuring

the social lab and integrate other case study approaches, where we will investigate and compare a wide range of cases.

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